

METHODS AND TECHNIQUES OF TRANSLATION

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Annotation: *When describing the translation process, researchers use such concepts as method, technique, method, each of which has its own content. A method is not an activity, not a system of actions, but a psychological operation that realizes an action. It is possible to go from one language to another to express an already formulated thought, to re-name the subject only by one of the existing methods of translation". What are these translations?*

Key words: *Transformation, linguistic sign, target language, lexical and grammatical transformation, analyzing, fundamental distinction.*

In the theory of translation, different ways, or ways of moving from units of one language to units of another language, were considered. In the first case, there is a direct transition from the signs of one language to the signs of another without referring to reality, that is, without analyzing the fragment of reality that is described in this segment of the text. In the second case, the translator, analyzing the meanings of the linguistic signs of the original, understands which particular fragment of reality is described in the original, and then describes the same fragment using the means of the target language. That is, in the process of interpretation, the translator, as it were, enters reality, and then returns to the system of the language, but already the target language. Such a fundamental distinction between two processes based on whether the translator refers to reality or not has been criticized in the literature, because it is clear that without analyzing the content of the text or its fragment, without understanding its meaning,

understanding what exactly is described in the text, successful translation is impossible. And, in principle, is not carried out.

Many authors consider any translation as a transformation, or interlingual transformation. Indeed, as a result of any translation, the plan of expression changes. Therefore, it can be argued that every translation is transformational. The assertion that translation is transformation gives the very term “transformation” an undesirable ambiguity. It turns out that transformation is both the transformation of units of one language into units of another language, that is, a certain translation operation, and the process of translation itself. Meanwhile, it can be assumed that some translations are more transformational, that is, they involve a greater number of transformations, while others are less transformational. It is indicative that L.S. Barkhudarov, in his work devoted to translation transformations considers as a transformational translation only that which is not carried out according to formal structural correspondences [3]. Transformational translation is opposed to the so-called interlinear translation, that is, translation carried out according to formal structural correspondences.

Consecutive interpreting uses the recording method. Recording, or cursive translation, is carried out according to certain rules and comes down to highlighting key or unique information in the orally perceived text of the original and fixing this information in writing using conventional signs, abbreviations and symbols. Based on the received record, the translator creates the text of the translation, while the record itself serves as a graphical embodiment of the main content quanta and the links between them.

Simultaneous translation uses the source text transformation method. The method of transformation of the source text in simultaneous translation aims to prepare the source text for operations at the formal sign level, that is, for the use of the sign method of translation. For this, it is provided:

- lexical transformations with the search for speech units included in the semantic (thematic) systems formed by the translator;

- grammatical transformations that take into account the most common and simple syntactic constructions of the target language;
- speech compression, which is achieved by using all possible types of transformation.

It is assumed that such preparatory operations allow the translator to relatively easily move from foreign language units and constructions to translation language units in the appropriate syntactic arrangement.

Attention is drawn, firstly, to the heterogeneity of the described methods of translation, which, however, can be regarded as a pattern, given the heterogeneity of the types of translation in which these methods are used. Secondly, a feature of these methods is their optionality: in principle, both written and simultaneous translation is possible without the use of these methods. Only consecutive interpreting is impossible without the use of the recording method, but it should be remembered that each interpreter can have his own recording system, which, however, is organized according to general principles. All this suggests that the creative nature of translation can lead (and possibly leads) to the creation of other methods of translation, individual for each translator. Therefore, it is hardly worth considering the method of translation as a general rule of translation.

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